

Mineralogical mapping of airless bodies of the Solar System

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The analysis of hyper- and multispectral remote sensing datasets is essential to investigate the mineralogy and the physical and chemical properties of a planetary surface. The mineralogy and the average composition of the surface of airless bodies observed today in our Solar System are the result of formation and evolution processes that occurred over geologic timescales. In the last decade, our knowledge on planetary surfaces improved considerably thanks to the datasets acquired by remote sensing instruments, such as cameras and spectrometers on board several space missions. Here, we show issues and potentialities of different hyper- and multispectral datasets aimed to the production and analysis of mineralogical and spectral indices maps of airless bodies of the Solar System.

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